

STUDY OF THE TOPIC OF OTTOMAN TOURISTS WHO TRAVELED TO CENTRAL ASIA

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Although the topic of Ottoman tourists with its rich history, especially the small Asian tourists who traveled to different parts of the world such as Africa and Europe, has been studied in some depth, it is in the Asian continent, especially in Central Asia, that the history, socio-political, economic and ethno-cultural aspects of these regions. The topic of tourists who witnessed the processes with their own eyes is not covered enough. However, Ottoman tourism, which has a history of almost five hundred years, stands out from others due to its consistency and focus on specific themes. It is interesting that the Ottoman tourists, who had some differences from the European, Iranian, Chinese, Russian and other tourists who traveled to Central Asia, approached the region in their own way. .

It should be mentioned at this point that the question of where and when the Oghuz Turks, who were the founders of this state in Ottoman society, migrated to Asia Minor and nearby regions was a controversial issue until the beginning of the 20th century, but most Ottoman authors attributed this migration to Turan or another name. They had certain ideas about their migration from the territories of Turkestan. In addition to the information contained in the works of Ottoman authors - historians, tourists, and writers - related to the Middle Ages, there are various written data (travel books, newspapers and magazines, letters, palace documents, etc.) related to the late Middle Ages, in particular, the middle of the 10th and 9th centuries - the beginning of the 20th century. the data confirmed.

The topic of Ottoman tourists in Central Asia, in general, the history of Central Asian-Ottoman relations was not sufficiently studied by historians of our region until recent years. One of the main reasons for this was the fact that in Soviet historiography, the detailed study of this issue, especially the research by Central

Asian researchers, was considered to strengthen nationalistic feelings. After the October coup, many Turkestan Jadids sought refuge abroad, in particular to Turkey, and the Soviet regime, as much as possible, prevented the searchers from Central Asian nations, including Uzbeks, Kazakhs, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, and Karakalpaks, from conducting research on this issue. Although there have been cases where representatives of the region have conducted research on this topic, they have often tried to keep this situation out of the general public's view.

As it has been mentioned, the researches carried out in Central Asia on the subject of Ottoman tourists who were in Central Asia and wrote down something about what they saw and experienced are quite lacking. The researchers focused briefly on the information recorded by tourists.

The works of Uzbek researchers, who translated the work of Seydi Ali Rais "Mir'otul Ma'molik" (Mirror of Countries) into Uzbek for the first time, wrote an introduction and scientific comments, and introduced it to the scientific community is noteworthy. This scientific publication carried out in the 1960s ¹ can be considered one of the first steps in illuminating the historical relations between Central Asia and Asia Minor. The authors of the publication did not limit themselves only to translations and scientific explanations, but also attached a number of maps, along with a much broader discussion of the life and work of Sayyid Ali Rais, as well as the socio-political environment of that time. At this point, it should be mentioned that this scientific publication, which is quite perfect for its time, has not yet received an adequate scientific assessment. For example, despite the fact that the work "Mir'otul Mamolik" has been published several times in Turkey, it is noticeable that there is almost no mention of the translation of the work into Uzbek, or a brief and general explanation is given.

Z. highlighted the issue of political and diplomatic relations between Central Asia, especially Bukhara, Kokand and Khiva khanates - the Ottoman Empire. It can be seen that Rahmankulova also touched on the topic of tourists ². It is noteworthy that

¹ Seydi Ali Rais. *Miratul Mamolik (Mirror of Countries) / Translation and Comments* I. Zunnunova's, editing and foreword by S. Azimjonova's. - Tashkent : Science, 1963.

² Rahmankulova Z.B. *The history of socio-political and cultural relations between Central Asia and the Ottoman state in the XVI-early XX century: candidate of history... dis.* – UzMU, 2002 ; Rahmankulova Z. *Rejuvenating S first Road : low present oath future of Turkey - Uzbekistan relations // 1 st Edition Istanbul In the morning Zaim university publications .*

the researcher was one of the first among the scientists of the region, and paid some attention to the information written down by Ottoman tourists. For example, it should be mentioned that the information provided by Seydi Ali Rais touched on the importance for the history of the region.

It should be mentioned that the relations between Central Asia and Iran, especially the works of Iranian authors who have been in the region and provide some extensive information about the people of the region, have not been sufficiently researched. However, from the Middle Ages to recent centuries, a number of Iranian ambassadors and tourists came from Iran to Central Asia, especially to the Khanates of Bukhara and Khiva, and based on them, it is possible to shed light on the hitherto little-studied aspects of the history of the region. The information written down by the Iranian authors is also similar to that of the Ottoman authors in a number of aspects, and it would be appropriate to carry out research comparing them. The common aspect of the historiography of both regions is that the Ottoman Turkish and Persian authors, based on the tradition of Muslim historiography, are related to the Turkic and Persian peoples in terms of ethnicity and know Central Asia better than others.

At this point, it should be mentioned that in some studies carried out in recent years, some attention is paid to the works of Iranian authors. In particular, the environment of Iran M. Hamdamova, on the basis of the information in the historical works created in Iran in the Middle Ages, it can be seen that during the Seljuks, Khorezmshah-Anushtegins and Timurids, the relations between the peoples of Central Asia and Asia Minor also received a little more attention³. The researcher tried to shed light on these issues by making extensive use of the work "History of Ambassador Nizamshah", which contains primary data for the history of both regions.

- Turkey , 2019. - P. 185-186; Rahmankulova Z. First The world is new Sava şı ve Turkey // International Asia and Africa Trade Congress . 38. ICANAS (Abstracts of Notices). - Ankara. 2007. – P. 30-41; Rakhmankulova Z., Choriev S., Yusupova D., Muminov O. The Historiography of The Relations Between Central Asian Khanates and Ottoman Empire in the 19th^{and} at the beginning of the 20th Centuries // International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research. Volume 9, Issue 02 , February 2020. – P. 311-318; Choriev Sh., Rakhmonkulova Z. Materialy lichnyx fondo v TsGA RUz o deyatelnosti russkikh vostokovedov v Turkestane // "Lichnost i vremya." Nikolay Ostroumov: vostokoved, prosvetitel, letopisets epoxi" - Mater.mejdunar.nauchn.conf. - Tashkent , 2016 . - C. 67-78 .

³Hamdamova M. "Historical ambassador Nizamshah" about the state of Anushtegini-Khorazmshahs // Social sciences in Uzbekistan. -Tashkent, 2001. - #6. - B. 72-75; Hamdamova M. Zarafshan oasis during the time of Amir Temur (based on the work "Tarihi elchi Nizamshah") // Proceedings of the Republican conference on Zarafshan oasis and its place in history: Tez.doc. - Samarkand, 2001. - B.133-134; Hamdamova M. History of Ambassador Nizamshah" About the State of the Seljuks // SaMSU Bulletin. - Samarkand, 2004. - №2, -B. 33-34; Hamdamova M. Kurt kings "History based on the work of Ambassador Nizamshah" // Collection. "Professor-teachers' scientific Proceedings of the theoretical conference, 2004. - B. Ahmedov A., M. Elchi Nizamshah's work on the relationship between the Timurids and the Safavids // Book 2 - Tashkent: 5-13.

Z., a researcher covering the history of Central Asia on the basis of information written by foreigners, especially European ambassadors and tourists. It is necessary to mention that in the research carried out by Saidboboev, works related to the Ottoman environment were also touched upon ⁴. As a specialist in the written sources of the period, the researcher paid attention to issues that had not been covered until now, which led to the fact that his research was well received by many.

S., who studied the history of the Timurid period, in particular, the diplomatic relations of this dynasty, the correspondence of Amir Temur. Ghulamov elaborates on the diplomatic relations between the Timurids and the Ottomans ⁵. It is necessary to mention that the researcher who paid attention to the diplomatic relations between Amir Temur and the Ottoman ruler Yildirim Bayazid, in particular the content of the correspondence between them, also touched upon the political and ethno-cultural relations between the peoples of both regions.

Sh. It is noteworthy that in Oljaeva's research, the issue of mutual relations between the peoples of both regions is somewhat more widely covered ⁶. The researcher's scientific works devoted to the medieval period of the history of the region, especially the history of the diplomatic relations of the Timurid era, attract attention.

It is worth noting that in recent years, research on the history of various khanates in the region - the Uzbek and Kazakh khanates - has also shed light on the historical relations between Central Asia and Asia Minor. In particular, each of the Uzbek khanates, such as Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand, established diplomatic relations with the Ottoman Empire, and in the process of studying the history of these khanates, we come across a number of researchers who have considered this issue separately for the example of each khanate. In particular, Sh. Shodieva, while shedding light on the role of the Ottoman rulers in the foreign policy of the Bukhara Emirate, draws attention to previously little-studied aspects of the issue, in particular, how the Ottoman court, one of the leading political forces of its time, reacted to the growing influence of the

⁴Saidboboev Z. A. Historical and cartographic information about Central Asia in Europe (XVI - XIX centuries): History science. name diss. - Tashkent, 2004.

⁵Gulomov S. Relations between Amir Temur and Bayazid // Sharkology. - Tashkent, 1996. - No. 7. - B. 7 4 -8 3.

⁶Oljaeva Sh. The beginning and development of diplomatic relations between Amir Temur and Yildirim Bayazid // Materials of the Republican scientific conference on the topic "Historical source studies, historiography and historical research method and methodology". - Tashkent, 2016. - B. 375-380.

Russians and the British in Turkestan ⁷. It is known that the Ottoman Empire's interest in the political fate of Central Asia, including the Emirate of Bukhara, intensified from the mid- 1970s . During this period, the main partner of this empire in the region was the Afghan Emirate, which became the center of ideas for promoting Muslim unity and liberating Bukhara, Khiva, and Turkestan in general, as evidenced by historical literature ⁸.

Sh., who paid attention to the fact that the warm relations between the Emirate of Bukhara and the Ottoman Turkish state continued at the beginning of the 19th century, are confirmed by the information presented in the historical literature. Shodieva emphasizes the decree of the Ottoman Turkish sultan on April 22, 1803, granting the ruler of Bukhara (Amir Haydar 1800-1826) the title of "King of Turkestan and Turan lands" ⁹. As will be discussed below, the fact that there is a tradition of Ottoman rulers awarding titles to Central Asian khanates, the question of which aspects the Ottoman court, which was well aware of the political processes in the region, paid attention to when awarding titles, requires a separate study. Certain diplomatic rules were followed when the titles were awarded, and it is clear that such titles were presented based on which khanate had the highest political authority in the region, and this issue was not treated superficially.

The topic of the history of relations between the Ottomans and the Koqan khanate also became more relevant in the following years. Q.Yo, who tried to illuminate the diplomatic relations of the Kokan Khanate with the example of relations established with the Ottomans. Akbarov dwells on the policy of the Ottoman sultans towards the Uzbek khanates, which rulers among the khanates they paid attention to ¹⁰. According to him, a letter written on September 10, 1820 on behalf of the Ottoman ruler in response to the letter of the Khan of Kokand, number 36579, has been preserved in the Khatti Humayun "Konsholik Maktublari" fund of the Ottoman

⁷Shodieva Sh.S. Regarding the diplomatic relations between the Emirate of Bukhara and the Ottoman Turkish state // Materials of the Republic-wide online scientific-practical conference on the topic "Bukhara's place in world culture". - Bukhara, 2020. - B. 173-176.

⁸Vasiliev A.D. The relationship between the Ottoman Empire and the republics of Central Asia in the middle of the 19th and late 20th centuries. Autoreferat na soiskanie uchennoy stepi candida istoricheskikh nauk. - M.: 2007. - S. 24; Shodieva Sh.S. From the history of relations between the B uxoro Emirate and the U Smonian Kingdom // Obrazovanie i innovatsionnye issledovaniya . 2022 , #11 . - B. 49.

⁹Shodieva Sh.S. From the history of relations between the B uxoro Emirate and the U Smonian kingdom . - B. 173-174.

¹⁰Akbarov Q.Yo. Diplomatic relations of the Kokan Khanate with the Ottoman state

archive. and Ferghana According to his address as "governor", it is clear that Umar Khan knew himself as the owner of the Kipchak Dashti territories, that is, the Kazakh steppes at that time ¹¹.

In the process of studying the foreign political and diplomatic history of Central Asian nations, the cases of referring to the information written by ambassadors and tourists are also found in the historiography of neighboring countries. In particular, it can be seen that in the following decades, Kyrgyz researchers paid much more attention to the diplomatic relations established with the Ottoman Empire in the example of the Kokan Khanate. For example, R. It is noteworthy that in the researches carried out by Abdiulova, on the basis of Ottoman documents and other materials, this issue was given a lot of attention ¹². Although the Kyrgyz researchers have tried to focus on the history of the Kyrgyz people, it is necessary to mention that they contribute to the illumination of the hitherto little-studied aspects of the activity of the Kokan Khans.

It is noteworthy that a number of researchers who focused on the issue of the establishment of Turkic dynasties in Asia Minor also paid attention to Central Asia in some places. In particular, the close political ties of the Ottomans to the region have been studied somewhat consistently by Turkish historians. In particular, the Turkish researcher F. In his large monograph "Oghuz (Turkmans)", Sumer covered the activities of the Seljuks in Central Asia, and it can be mentioned that in some places the researcher briefly touched on the past of the Ottoman dynasty in these regions.

In the following years, the Azerbaijani orientalist Sh. It can be seen that Mustafaev paid some attention to the relations established with Central Asia during both dynasties ¹³. It should be mentioned here that Sh. To this day, Mustafaev highlighted the relationship between Central Asia and the Ottoman Empire, which has been overlooked by most researchers. Persian language created during the rule of the dynasties He also touched on the information in the works ¹⁴.

¹¹Akbarov Q.Yo. Diplomatic relations of the Kokan Khanate with the Ottoman state. - B. 289.

¹²Abdulova R. 19th Archival materials related to the diplomatic ties between the Kingdom of Heaven and the Kokon trenches // Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi. Issue: 15, 2006. - S. 1-20.

¹³ Mustafaev Sh. Ot Seldjukov k asmanam. Ethnopolitical processes in the Turkic environment of Malay Asia in the XI-XV centuries. - M.: B.i., 2017.

¹⁴ Mustafayev Sh. Safevi Tarih Yazımında Osmanlılar (Şah İsmail ve Şah Tahmasb Devirleri) // Türk Tarihi Araştırmaları Dergisi / Journal of Turkish History Researches, Yıl/Vol. 3, Number/No. 1 Bahar/Spring 2018. - P. 1-49.

Hsao Komatsu, a Japanese historian of Middle Asia studies the relations between the two regions on the example of the Kokan Khanate ¹⁵, and it is understood that the Ottoman Empire also touched on the issue of other khanates in the region and put forward some interesting ideas comparing the content and essence of the relations between them. At this point, it should be mentioned that in the following decades, it is noticeable that Japanese researchers are covering the history of the Ottoman Empire and the Central Asian khanates, in particular, the issue of foreign relations.

Russian historian A.D., who conducted a number of studies on political and diplomatic relations between Central Asia and the Ottoman Empire in recent years. Vasiliev's research is noteworthy ¹⁶. Based on written sources in Ottoman, Russian and other languages, the researcher was able to shed light on the hitherto little-studied aspects of the history of the Khans in the region. In his research, the issue of the process of conquest of Central Asia by Tsarist Russia and the policy of the Ottoman sultans in this matter was raised, and it is distinguished by its reliance on primary data.

Thus, the written sources belonging to the Ottoman environment illuminating the history of Central Asia, in particular, the information written down by the small Asian ambassadors and tourists, make a unique contribution to giving certain ideas about the socio-political and ethno-cultural life of the inhabitants of both regions. Although special studies that provide full historical insights have not been conducted within the scope of the topic, and most researchers have touched on the issue from the point of view of political and diplomatic relations of the Central Asia - Asia Minor regions, it is noteworthy that in some places they have also paid attention to the information of Ottoman tourists.

¹⁵Komatsu N. Kokand and Istanbul. An Ottoman Document Relating to the Earliest Contact between the Khan and the Sultan. – Barukan Shouajia Kenkyu (Balkan and Asia Minor Studies), No. 15, 1989.

¹⁶ Vasiliev A.D. The relationship between the Ottoman Empire and the republics of Central Asia in the middle of the 19th and late 20th centuries. Autoref. k.i.n. - Moscow, 2007; Vasiliev A.D. "Znamya i mech ot padishakha". Political and cultural contacts between Central Asia and the Ottoman Empire (mid-16th - late 20th centuries). - M., 2014 ; Vasiliev A.D. "Bukhara is similar to Aljiru": the Ottoman politicheskaya elita on the request of the Bukharan Emir Haidara Sultanu Mahmud II on the prinyatii Bukhari v sostav Osmanskoy imperii / Vostok. 2021, No. 4 . - S. 83-94.